

SOLARIZE Survey Results (I)

D3.1

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Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This report corresponds to deliverable 3.1 of the SOLARIZE project. Its primary objective is to gather input from the renewable energies research and industrial community, aiming to identify services and infrastructure needed to meet both current demands and emerging trends in Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) and related renewable technologies. For this goal, a survey was prepared and distributed among participants in two SOLARIZE events organized until the date of the assessment.

Due to limited in-person project activities prior to the date of writing this report, outreach efforts included online channels (LinkedIn, emails) and distributed by the Horizon Europe project CST4ALL, which has some similar goals as SOLARIZE¹. The survey featured twelve questions across four thematic areas: participant background, infrastructure needs, technology synergies, and interest in collaboration.

As of June 18, 2025, a total of 41 responses were received. Most participants were researchers based in research institutes and universities, with additional input from technology developers and industry actors. While the responses spanned several countries—Germany, France, Spain, Türkiye, Italy, Greece—the sample was not fully balanced geographically, indicating the need for broader outreach in future phases.

The majority of respondents reported working with CST technologies, while a significant portion also brought expertise in energy storage, photovoltaics (PV), concentrated PV (CPV), and other renewable energy applications. Among the infrastructure needs identified were solar thermal testing and characterization

¹ The EU-funded CST4ALL (GA nr. 101075408) project seeks to identify an array of hybridisation initiatives between concentrated solar thermal power and other technologies for three sectors: electricity, heat and fuels. The project conducted a set of workshops with research and industrial stakeholders to better coordinate technology improvements. The idea is to expand the Concentrated Solar Power Implementation Working Group in the SET Plan and to raise general awareness about the role it can play in a future sustainable energy mix. The project will also create specific EU-level proposals for a political/regulatory framework.

(including component performance and thermal characterization), energy storage and grid integration, simulation and modelling (emphasis on energy storage modelling), materials testing (e.g., aging, characterization and irradiation studies) and solar fuels and water treatment (notably hydrogen and desalination).

Access to research infrastructure was viewed as most valuable when it facilitated collaboration, offered technical expertise, was affordable, and easily accessible. Environmental and ethical aspects were also appreciated, reflecting a shift toward responsible and sustainable research practices.

Participants also expressed strong interest in synergies between CST and other technologies. They identified opportunities in hybrid systems that integrate CST with PV, hydrogen production, and thermal storage, as well as applications in industrial process heat, district heating, and desalination. The most common barriers to collaboration cited were lack of funding and poor communication, while technical incompatibility was seen as a minor concern.

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All respondents showed interest in sharing knowledge and best practices. Joint research projects and in-person gatherings such as workshops and conferences were viewed as the most effective formats for collaboration, while online platforms and commercial events were seen as less impactful in building trust and connection.

Abbreviations

CSP	Concentrated Solar Power
CST	Concentrated Solar Thermal
CPV	Concentrated photovoltaics
EU	European Union
HTF	Heat transfer fluid
MS	Microsoft
PSA	Plataforma Solar de Almería
PV	Photovoltaics
RI	Research Infrastructure
UK	United Kingdom
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Description of the Task

Deliverable 3.1 “Survey results” is related to SOLARIZE **Task 3.1 “Identification of new services and facilities to cover current and emerging needs”**, led by DLR with support from all project partners. This task is divided in two main parts; the first one, covered in this deliverable, is dedicated to identifying services and facilities required by external users, and the second part, covered in deliverable 3.4, is dedicated to collecting information to assess the services currently offered by the EU-SOLARIS partners and other relevant European centres dedicated to Concentrated Solar Thermal CST research and development.

To find out which services and facilities are needed by its users, Task 3.1 defines this information about the infrastructure requirements via input gathered through surveys and interviews with the key stakeholders. This will be integrated during events organized by SOLARIZE, such as the national events, summer schools and doctoral colloquia in WP1 and the industrial trainings and workshops in WP2.

The information should be provided mainly by technology providers in Europe, plant operators, technology developers and researchers in order to get a direct input from the potential users regarding the needs for new services and infrastructure. In addition, societal needs and implications will be considered to identify solutions that will support technology acceptance and also encapsulate aspects such as environmental, economic and ethical impact. Emphasis will be given to reach a wider user community, also considering the requirements of other technologies that can profit from the infrastructure created mainly for CST research, such as meteorological measurement equipment and collected data, material aging tests, optical and thermal measurement systems, etc.

This is the first version of the deliverable. A second version is planned for project month 24 and a third version by project month 36.

1.2 Methodology

As indicated in the task description, the surveys to obtain the relevant data were to be distributed during the events organized by the SOLARIZE project. Up to the time this deliverable was to be submitted only two project events were planned, namely the Doctoral Colloquium and Summer School led by CIEMAT in Almeria, Spain, between June 2nd and 6th 2025. Therefore, additional measures were taken to reach a higher number of survey respondents and, therefore, increase the statistical meaning of the results. The Task responsible, DLR, and the Project Coordinator, EU-SOLARIS, decided to expand the outreach of the survey and make it public in SOLARIZE's website² and distribute the announcement to the survey via different channels: SOLARIZE'S LinkedIn account, direct emails to the contacts of the project partners, announcement during the 5th Industry workshop of the project CST4ALL³ and through the stakeholders contact of the project CST4ALL, which has similar goals of creating synergies between Concentrated Solar Thermal and other renewable technologies⁴.

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To assess the results of the survey, the form embedded in SOLARIZE's website is able to export the results in a Google Sheet. Then this was saved as an MS Excel file and formulas were used to count the different types of answers and diagrams were created.

² <https://solarize-project.eu/surveys/>

³ <https://cst4all.eu/en/4039-events-cst4all>

⁴ The EU-funded CST4ALL (GA nr. 101075408) project seeks to identify an array of hybridisation initiatives between concentrated solar thermal power and other technologies for three sectors: electricity, heat and fuels. The project conducted a set of workshops with research and industrial stakeholders to better coordinate technology improvements. The idea is to expand the Concentrated Solar Power Implementation Working Group in the SET Plan and to raise general awareness about the role it can play in a future sustainable energy mix. The project will also create specific EU-level proposals for a political/regulatory framework.

2. Main Outcomes

2.1 About the survey

The survey can be answered online by anyone accessing the SOLARIZE's website (<https://solarize-project.eu/surveys/>). The survey begins with information on the goals and scope of the survey, as shown in its introduction copied below:

"This survey aims to identify current and emerging needs for Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) research facilities and the services they offer and explore synergies with other renewable energy technologies. The outcomes of this survey will contribute to an optimal design of the EU-SOLARIS ERIC. Therefore, your inputs are crucial for shaping the future renewable energy research landscape in Europe, in which cross-cutting technology leadership is on the top priorities.

This survey will be disseminated through various channels, including international events, project workshops, and targeted outreach to relevant research communities. Interviews will also be conducted to gather more in-depth information. All data collected will be treated confidentially and used solely for the purpose of the project SOLARIZE".

The survey is structured in 4 sections: 1) Personal Data, 2) Current & Future Needs for Renewable Energy Research Infrastructure, 3) Synergy Potential & Cross-Cutting Applications and 4) Best Practice Exchange & Collaboration. It consists of 12 questions of the type multiple choice, ranking and open ended. Annex 1 shows the questions asked. Name and email of the respondents was optionally to be entered only to enlarge the project stakeholders data base, personal data was not used for the assessment in this deliverable. Information of the name of the organization to which the respondent belongs is also not published.

Finally, the survey ends with a Data Protection Policy agreement copied below. It is to be mentioned that all responses received until the date of writing this report answer positively to the Data Protection Policy.

“Data Protection Policy

Do you agree to receive future communications related to similar activities, events, or initiatives organized by the SOLARIZE Project?

In accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of April 27, 2016, General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), we inform you that the personal data you provide in connection with the Infrastructure Needs & Synergy Potential Survey will be incorporated into a database managed by the SOLARIZE Project. This data will be used for the purpose of managing your participation in the survey. Additionally, aggregated and anonymized data from the survey may be published to support the identification of synergies between technologies, promote the use of research infrastructures (RI), and inform strategic development in related fields. No personally identifiable information will be disclosed in any published results. The legal basis for processing your data is your explicit consent, provided by completing the survey form. Your data will be retained only as long as necessary to fulfil the stated purposes and will not be shared with third parties without your authorization, unless legally required. You have the right to access, rectify, erase, restrict, or object to the processing of your data, as well as the right to data portability. You may exercise these rights at any time by contacting us at info@solarize-project.eu. You may also withdraw your consent at any time without affecting the lawfulness of processing carried out prior to withdrawal. For further details, please refer to our Privacy Policy available at <https://solarize-project.eu/>.”

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2.2 Survey Results and findings

As of June 18, 2025, the survey was completed by 41 respondents. A summary of their answers and the analysis of the outcomes is presented in the following sections.

2.2.1 Profile of the Participants in the Survey

The first part of the survey collects information about the profile of the participants. Figure 1 shows the participants role in the company or institution reflecting participants' position to support a view in their expertise area. The vast majority of the participants are researchers (71%) followed by technology developers (17%) and only very few responses from technology providers, plant operators and others. Figure 2 shows the organization type in which the respondent works, the majority belongs to research institutes (52%), followed by Universities (25%) and then private companies (23%); it is to be noted that some respondents work at different organization types simultaneously, therefore the total distribution sum exceeds 100%. For the scope of this study it would be very helpful to have a better-balanced profile of the respondents, specially having a higher sample from the industry.

Figure 1: Respondents' working role

Figure 2: Respondents' organization type

Regarding the country from which the respondent come, as shown in Figure 3, 22% are from Germany or France, followed by Spain (15%), Turkiye (10%), Italy and Greece with 7%. Single participants come from Algeria, Denmark, Morocco, Portugal, Sudan, Sweden and the UK. The obtained country distribution is also not well balanced, as it would be ideal to receive more answers from member and observer countries of EU-SOLARIS such as Cyprus, Greece and Portugal.

Figure 3: Respondents' Country

An important piece of information to assess the results of the survey is the primary expertise area of the respondents. In this case, many respondents marked several answers (92 fields marked by 41 respondents). Probably due to the interest of the respondents in the project SOLARIZE, as shown in Figure 4 the larger fraction of expertise is on Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST) (37%), followed by Energy Storage (21%), Concentrated Photovoltaics (14%), Non-Concentrated Photovoltaics (10%) and Non-Concentrated Solar Thermal (8%). Other fields of renewable energy (Biomass, Geothermal, and Wind) correspond to 10% or less of the answers. This result is important because it means that 63% of the areas of expertise marked are from fields other than CST, meaning that there is a good source of information to assess the needs and synergy potential of renewable energy technologies different than CST.

Figure 4: Respondents' Field of Expertise

2.2.2 Current & Future Needs for Renewable Energy Research Infrastructure

The 6th question on the survey has to do with the research services or facilities used or foresee needed by the respondents. This information will be useful to compare it with services currently offered or planned by EU-SOLARIS or other European research centres. This section is divided into 5 different topics, the percentage of votes given to each topic is shown in Table 1. In many cases, respondents marked more than one option, the results shown in Table 2 to Table 6 are percentage of activities marked per topic.

Table 1: Selection of Topics for Research Services or Infrastructure Needs

28%	Solar Thermal Testing and Characterization
21%	Grid Integration and Energy Storage
20%	Modelling and Simulation
20%	Material Synthesis and Characterization
10%	Solar Fuels, Chemistry and Water Treatment

Table 2: Research Services or Infrastructure Needs regarding Solar Thermal Testing and Characterization

18.7%	Performance and characterization of plant components (receivers, reactors, thermal storage, heat exchangers, etc.)
15.1%	Thermal characterization of solar absorbers
13.7%	Operation and maintenance procedures for solar collectors and heliostats
13.7%	Accelerated aging of plant components
12.9%	Optical characterization of mirrors
9.4%	Material testing under high temperatures (up to 3500 °C) and high solar fluxes
7.9%	Heliostat beam and tracking accuracy characterization
6.5%	Characterization of equipment for molten salt loops
2.2%	Others

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Table 3: Research Services or Infrastructure Needs regarding Solar Fuels, Chemistry and Water Treatment

31%	Solar hydrogen production
27%	Research and validation for solar thermal desalination
24%	Design and test of solar chemistry applications
14%	Solar photocatalytic treatment and disinfection of wastewaters
4%	Others

Table 4: Research Services or Infrastructure Needs regarding Grid Integration and Energy Storage

21.0%	Testing of thermal storage systems and sub-systems
21.0%	Validating simulation models of thermal storage systems
21.0%	Testing and characterization of full-scale electrical energy storage systems
11.4%	Evaluation of photovoltaic systems with grid integration
10.5%	Energy management testing and optimization
7.6%	Real-time monitoring and control of micro-grids
7.6%	Testing of micro-grid components
0.0%	Others

Table 5: Research Services or Infrastructure Needs regarding Modelling and Simulation

23%	Energy storage modelling
20%	Optical simulations of solar concentrating systems
19%	Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations
18%	Transient system simulations
18%	Detailed system design and optimization for energy mix/hybrid systems
2%	Others

Table 6: Research Services or Infrastructure Needs regarding Material Synthesis and Characterization

19%	Materials and coatings analysis
18%	Characterization of optical, surface, and electrical properties of materials
18%	Irradiation studies and characterization of aging effects
15%	Corrosion detection and prevention, anti-corrosive protection systems, durability evaluation
10%	Synthesis of advanced nanomaterials
9%	Thin film deposition, nano/micro-structuring
6%	High throughput electrochemical characterization for conductive materials
4%	High throughput high-temperature casting for metals and alloys
1%	Others

Regarding the access to research infrastructures, question 7 seeks to obtain information on the importance of key parameters such as accessibility, affordability, data management and sharing capabilities, technical expertise and support staff, collaboration opportunities, and environmental and ethical impact. Figure 5 to Figure 10 show the percentage of votes per importance level (5: very important, 1: not important). The average of all votes obtained per category helps to rank the parameter most important for the respondents as follows:

1. Collaboration opportunities (avg. 4,51 points)
2. Technical expertise & support staff (avg. 4,41 points)
3. Affordability (cost of using services) (avg. 4,39 points)
4. Accessibility (ease of access, booking procedures) (avg. 4.34 points)
5. Environmental and ethical impact (avg, 4,07 points)

The differences between the categories are quite small (less than 0,5 points) and all of them are ranked above 4 points, meaning that all these parameters seem to be very relevant with respect to access to research infrastructure. It is interesting to see that the human aspects, namely the collaboration opportunities and the technical expertise and support of the staff got the highest values while the lowest values was obtained for the environmental and ethical impact.

Figure 5: Importance of Accessibility

Figure 6: Importance of Affordability

Figure 7: Importance of Data Management and Sharing Capabilities

Figure 8: Importance of Technical Expertise & Support Staff

Figure 9: Importance of Collaboration Opportunities

Figure 10: Importance of Environmental and Ethical Impact

2.2.3 Synergy Potential & Cross-Cutting Applications

The 8th question was an open-ended question about the potential synergies between CST and the working field of the respondent. For this case, the most interesting answers are from respondents working on fields different than CST. Therefore the 4 answers received from these other sectors are copied below:

- CST can provide vast amounts of heat for the realization of endothermal thermocatalytic reactions, that can be part of cycles for the production of solar fuels in industrial scale
- There is no need in Germany so far to apply CST in agrivoltaic systems. But we already had questions like these from municipalities, researchers and farmers if it is applicable with their planned district heating net close to the potential agrivoltaic facility. The question always arose if it's feasible with the HTF (e.g. glycol) in an agricultural field and how the light sharing with CST and crops would look like.
- Thermal Energy Storages
- To make the power plants more efficient with long life we need to hybridize it especially the parabolic trough power plant with PV plant and hydrogen production as mean of storage and fuel cells.

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13 respondents that work with CST and other fields gave the following answers:

- Already actively involved in the field.
- Combination of inexpensive flat plate collectors and concentrating tracking collectors
- CST could pre-heat water for high temperature catalyses of hydrogen gas which we aim to develop in Cyprus, whit several partners.
- High-temperature materials developments
- I am interested in green hydrogen production and storage using CST.
- Improvement of energy performance using advanced simulation tools and innovative designs
- Maximising efficiency of CST systems through planning, forecasting and advanced control.

- ODTU-GUNAM and METUWind are one of the, if not the, largest PV and Wind CoEs, respectively, in the E. Med. Turkiye has the largest geothermal resources in Europe.
- Research
- RI provider
- The implementation of the CST in industrial process
- The use of CST for metallurgy
- We are operating a Concentrated Solar Thermal power plant

Finally, the answers from only CST involved people were the following:

- Company will provide CST.
- CST+Desalination, CST+Industry, hot air processes, CST+Grid integration
- CST+Desalination, CST+Grid integration, CST+Industrial process with hot air
- Full synergies, I work an engineering and consultant company specialized in CST.
- My reactor design will be energetically driven by CST
- Plant design and operation optimisation. Dispatch strategy
- This is my field
- This is our key technology

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The 9th open question was about existing infrastructure at the respondent's organization that could be used by CST researchers. These were the answers from non-CST experts:

- Non existent
- Please contact the CST department at my company for this.

Respondents that work with CST and other technologies wrote the following:

- a 1.6 kW solar simulator (xenon lamp with an elliptical mirror)
- A small CST installation
- Advanced open source CSP modelling, Wind tunnel characterization of components
- All of them

- DLR Synlight in Jülich, DLR High-flux Solar Furnace and Solar Simulator in Collogne, DLR MOPUW installation in Cologne
- Materials testing at high temperatures
- Microsol-R, Odeillo furnace
- MoPuW
- Solar simulator, solar furnace, PTC-like installation.
- Solar simulator. Material characterization.
- Solarus Renewables is one of the owners the company SolaPeak that has a laboratory with capability to manufacture prototypes through 3D-printing and other technics and withe a large solar simulator.
- Test facilities for heat stores and solar collectors
- We could share data from our power plant
- We have in the past written project proposals related to CST+green hydrogen. That can be put on the rooftop of our university building. I can discuss the project idea if needed.

Finally, the answers from CST involved people were the following:

- In-cloud collaborative platform to techno-economic optimisation of plant design and operation. Also for components and costs sensitivity analysis
- Linear Fresnel concentrator ($S=10m^2$), Parabolic trough ($S=25m^2$)
- None. We are not a lab, we use labs.
- Not so much as the facilities are not ours.
- PSA infrastructure, central tower receiver, desalination, parabolic trough,...
- PSA is already participating in this alliance and providing its infrastructure
- solar furnace, solar simulator(s).

Finally, the 10th question of the survey was on the main barriers to realize these synergies. The distribution of answers is shown in Figure 11. The majority report funding limitations as the main barrier (53%), followed by lack of communication (35%). Two of the "others" responses reported limited staff as a barrier. Technical barriers (incompatible equipment) was selected only 3

times (6%). It is clear from this that changes in funding policy and support to communications actions should allow for more effective synergies between sectors, although the sample size of the answers gathered is still quite low.

Figure 11: Main Barriers to Synergies

2.2.4 Best Practice Exchange & Collaboration

The last section of the survey seeks to gain knowledge on the collaboration potential. To the question "Are you interested in knowledge exchange" all respondents (100%) answered yes. The distribution of areas of interest is shown in Figure 12. The fields more voted are: CST (28%), Energy Storage (22%) and Non-Concentrated Solar Thermal (13%), the rest of the fields make up to 37% combined but not surpassing 9% each. For the field "Others" (7%), the following answers were received: Hydrogen gas, Abiotic theory of hydrocarbons, Chemtrail effects on solar energy, Catalyst development, Materials science, Agrivoltaics and Heat pumps. These outcomes can help to identify topics for communication and dissemination events in Europe.

Figure 12: Areas of interest for knowledge exchange

Finally, the answers to the most effective ways to foster collaboration are shown in Figure 13. It can be seen that the distribution is quite uniform, with most of the answers for Joint research and innovation projects (30%), followed by Workshops (23%) and Conferences (20%). The least selected options are Joint commercial applications (15%) and Online platforms (12%). These results also show indirectly that funding for joint projects is required to achieve collaboration between sectors. Workshops and conferences, normally related to project results, are also good ways of collaboration.

Figure 13: Most effective ways to foster collaboration

3. Conclusions

This deliverable presented the preliminary results of the “Infrastructure Needs & Synergy Potential Survey” promoted by SOLARIZE. The deliverable has included input from 41 survey responses from the events conducted under the project and other communication measures. In the coming timeline, the content will be enriched with extra respondents from upcoming project events. The next update of the deliverable is planned in one year from now (June 2026). Based on the current results, trends can be identified and also some actions to reach a wider stakeholders group and thus increase the statistical values of the answers. The key outcomes from the current data collected are listed below:

- The vast majority of the participants are researchers (71%) followed by technology developers (17%) and only very few responses from technology providers, plant operators and others.
- The majority belongs to research institutes (52%), followed by Universities (25%) and then private companies (23%); some respondents work partially at different organization types.
- For the scope of this study it would be very helpful to have a better-balanced profile of the respondents, specially having a higher sample from the industry.
- 22% participants were from Germany or France, followed by Spain (15%), Turkiye (10%), Italy and Greece with 7%. Single participants come from Algeria, Denmark, Morocco, Portugal, Sudan, Sweden and UK. It would be ideal to receive more answers from member and observer countries of EU-SOLARIS such as Cyprus, Greece and Portugal.
- Regarding field of expertise 37% belong to CST, followed by Energy Storage (21%), Concentrated Photovoltaics (14%), Non-Concentrated Photovoltaics (10%) and Non-Concentrated Solar Thermal (8%). Other fields of renewable energy (Biomass, Geothermal, and Wind) have 10% or less of the answers. This result is important because it means that 63% of the areas of expertise marked are from fields other than CST, meaning that there is a good source of information to assess the needs and synergy potential of renewable energy technologies different than CST.

- Regarding the research services or facilities used or foresee needing by the respondents, the spread between options is quite uniform, and the most selected fields are the following:
 - Performance and characterization of plant components (receivers, reactors, thermal storage, heat exchangers, etc.)
 - Thermal characterization of solar absorbers
 - Operation and maintenance procedures for solar collectors and heliostats
 - Accelerated aging of plant components
 - Optical characterization of mirrors
 - Solar hydrogen production
 - Research and validation for solar thermal desalination
 - Design and test of solar chemistry applications
 - Testing of thermal storage systems and sub-systems
 - Validating simulation models of thermal storage systems
 - Testing and characterization of full-scale electrical energy storage systems
 - Energy storage modelling
 - Optical simulations of solar concentrating systems
 - Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations
 - Transient system simulations
 - Detailed system design and optimization for energy mix/hybrid systems
 - Materials and coatings analysis
 - Characterization of optical, surface, and electrical properties of materials
 - Irradiation studies and characterization of aging effects
 - Corrosion detection and prevention, anti-corrosive protection systems, durability evaluation
- The ranking on the most important parameters to allow access to services and/or facilities is:
 - Collaboration opportunities (avg. 4,51 points)
 - Technical expertise & support staff (avg. 4,41 points)
 - Affordability (cost of using services) (avg. 4,39 points)

- Accessibility (ease of access, booking procedures) (avg. 4.34 points)
- Environmental and ethical impact (avg, 4,07 points)
- Regarding synergies with CST, hybridization to make use of the heat and/or the storage capabilities of CST are mentioned.
- On the question of main barriers to achieve synergies, the majority report funding limitations as the main barrier (53%), followed by lack of communication (35%). Technical barriers (incompatible equipment) had only 6% of the answers.
- 100% of the respondents are interested in knowledge exchange channels. With the fields more voted being CST (28%), Energy Storage (22%) and Non-Concentrated Solar Thermal (13%).
- Ways to foster collaboration are joint research and innovation projects (30%), followed by Workshops (23%) and Conferences (20%). The least selected options are Joint commercial applications (15%) and On-line platforms (12%).

Annex 1: Survey screenshots

Section 1: Personal data

1. Role

- Technology Provider
- Plant Operator
- Technology Developer
- Researcher
- Policy
- Other

Other (please specify)

2. Organization Name

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3. Organization Type

- University
- Research Institute
- Private Company
- NGO
- Other

Other (please specify)

4. Country

5. Primary Research/Business Area

- Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST)
- Non-Concentrating Solar Thermal
- Concentrating Photovoltaics (CPV)
- Non-Concentrating Photovoltaics (PV)
- Wind Energy
- Geothermal
- Biomass
- Energy Storage
- Other

Other (please specify)

Figure 14: Section 1 of the survey (questions 1 to 5)

Section 2: Current & Future Needs for Renewable Energy Research Infrastructure

6. Research services/facilities you use or foresee needing

Solar Thermal Testing and Characterization

- Optical characterization of mirrors
 - Accelerated aging of plant components
 - Thermal characterization of solar absorbers
 - Material testing under high temperatures (up to 3500 °C) and high solar fluxes
 - Performance and characterization of plant components (receivers, reactors, thermal storage, heat exchangers, etc.)
 - Heliostat beam and tracking accuracy characterization
 - Operation and maintenance procedures for solar collectors and heliostats
 - Characterization of equipment for molten salt loops
 - Others
-

Solar Fuels, Chemistry and Water Treatment

- Solar photocatalytic treatment and disinfection of wastewaters
 - Solar hydrogen production
 - Research and validation for solar thermal desalination
 - Design and test of solar chemistry applications
 - Others
-

Grid Integration and Energy Storage

- Testing and characterization of full-scale electrical energy storage systems
- Testing of thermal storage systems and sub-systems
- Validating simulation models of thermal storage systems
- Evaluation of photovoltaic systems with grid integration
- Energy management testing and optimization
- Testing of micro-grid components
- Real-time monitoring and control of micro-grids
- Others

Modelling and Simulation

- Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulations
- Transient system simulations
- Optical simulations of solar concentrating systems
- Energy storage modelling
- Detailed system design and optimization for energy mix/hybrid systems
- Others

Material Synthesis and Characterization

- Characterization of optical, surface, and electrical properties of materials
- Materials and coatings analysis
- Corrosion detection and prevention, anti-corrosive protection systems, durability evaluation
- Irradiation studies and characterization of aging effects
- Synthesis of advanced nanomaterials
- High throughput high-temperature casting for metals and alloys
- High throughput electrochemical characterization for conductive materials
- Thin film deposition, nano/micro-structuring
- Others

7. How important are the following aspects? (1 = not important, 5 = very important)

Accessibility (ease of access, booking procedures):

Affordability (cost of using services):

Data management & sharing capabilities:

Technical expertise & support staff:

Collaboration opportunities:

Environmental and ethical impact:

Figure 15: Section 2 of the survey (questions 6 to 7)

Section 3: Synergy Potential & Cross-Cutting Applications

8. What potential synergies do you see between CST and your field?

9. What existing infrastructure at your organization could be used by CST researchers?

10. What are the main barriers to realizing these synergies?

- Lack of communication
- Incompatible equipment
- Funding limitations
- Conflicts of interest
- Other

Figure 16: Section 3 of the survey ((questions 8 to 10)

Section 4: Best Practice Exchange & Collaboration

11. Are you interested in knowledge exchange?

- Yes
- No

Areas of interest (if yes)

- Concentrated Solar Thermal (CST)
- Non-Concentrating Solar Thermal
- Concentrating Photovoltaics (CPV)
- Non-Concentrating Photovoltaics (PV)
- Wind Energy
- Geothermal
- Biomass
- Energy Storage
- Other

12. Most effective ways to foster collaboration?

- Joint research and innovation projects
- Joint commercial applications
- Workshops
- Conferences
- Online platforms
- Other

Figure 17: Section 4 of the survey (questions 11 to 12)